

VillageMath Educational Review

An International/Multidisciplinary Journal of
Network for Grassroots Science and Mathematics
Education (The VillageMath Network)

A publication of VillageMath Educational Services
(CAC RC: 4097888)

Volume 4, Issue 1

September, 2022

CODEN: VERIAU

Physics Students' Perception of Physics Concepts as Difficult and the Perception of their Performance in the Subject in Benue State, Nigeria

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7108848

Article History: Received 5th September, 2022; Revised 15th September, 2022; Published 23rd September, 2022.

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How to Cite this Article:

Taangahar, B. A. & Okwori, A. (2022). Physics Students' Perception of Physics Concepts as Difficult and the Perception of their Performance in the Subject in Benue State, Nigeria. *VillageMath Educational Review (VER)*, 4(1), 16-25.
<https://ngsme.villagemath.net/journals/ver/v4i1/taangahar-okwori>

Abstract

The study compares students' perception of physics concepts as difficult and the perception of their performance in secondary schools in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. It was guided by five research questions and three hypotheses. The sample of the study was made up of 150 SS2 students from 5 schools in the Local Government Area. The instrument for the study was a researcher-structured questionnaire named: Students' Perception of Difficult Concepts and the Perception of their Performance in the Physics Questionnaire. The instruments' reliability using Cronbach Alpha scored a coefficient of 0.62 and 0.75. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study established that students' perception of physics concepts as difficult provided a high mean score of 2.87 above the benchmark for decision-making of 2.50 and a low students' perception of their performance in the subject with a mean

score of 1.84 below the same benchmark. Physics students' mean perception score of physics concepts as difficult did not significantly differ from the mean perception of their performance score in the subject ($p = 0.12 > \alpha = 0.05$). Physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult and the perception of their performance in the subject did not significantly differ based on gender. It was recommended that teachers should reduce abstraction in the teaching physics concepts perceived by students as difficult.

Keywords: Physics Education, Difficult Concepts, Academic Performance, Difficult Physics Concepts, Gender

Introduction

Science is considered a potent tool for finding solutions to the persistent human problems. According to Okoro (2013) science is a systematic investigation of nature with a view to harnessing it to serve human needs. In acquiring knowledge from nature, the scientific process, which involves inquiry skills of observing, classifying, experimenting, measuring and organizing data, is used. Science at secondary school level in Nigeria is offered in subjects like chemistry, biology and physics.

Physics is the study of matter and energy and how they affect each other (Adeyemo, 2010). It is a core subject at senior secondary school level in Nigeria. Secondary school physics content consist of mechanics, kinematics, fluid mechanics, thermodynamics, oscillation and waves, atomic and nuclear as well as particle physics. It is a requirement for entry into higher institutions in Nigeria for further study of science, engineering, aviation, astronomy and medicine. It can also be employed in many sectors of the economy for national development. Despite the importance of physics to national development, it appears most physics students perceive a number of physics concepts as difficult.

Students' perception of concepts could refer to how they view, observe or consider such concepts. The perception process essentially involves sensory stimulation and selection, organization as well as interpretation. This process automatically occurs in an individual's cognitive structure. Thus, the extent to which students perceive a concept as difficult or not, largely depends on the manner it is taught and the performance of the students. According to Nava and Camarao (2017), students perceive that teaching, which emphasises more on solving problems, was a major source of difficulty for them. Bello, Opaleye and Olatunde (2018) posited that physics students' consideration of concepts as difficult were mostly concepts with too many formulae and laws and those with too much calculations but little practical work.

Physics concepts are considered difficult when an academically average student performs poorly when evaluated. This is especially when the teacher has put in his best in a series of instructional delivery (Omiko, 2017). According to Nava and Camarao (2017) physics students find mechanics, optics, electromagnetism and thermodynamics difficult to understand. Bello, Opaleye and Olatunde (2018) revealed that simple harmonic motion, projectiles, waves and gas laws among others were mostly considered difficult. Akongu, Nwona and Obo (2020) reported physics students perceived difficult concepts to involve waves, electricity, magnetism, nuclear physics, pressure and simple harmonic motion.

Students' perception of physics concept as difficult is suspected to influence their performance in the subject.

Performance, in education, is the attainment of an objective in a manner that ensures that the performer has attained set goals in a given level of education (Butts, Clery, Abeywardana & Phillips, 2017). Even though it is expected that students' performance in physics be high due to its importance to the development of a nation, Abah, Ada, Taangahar (2016) pointed out that students' performance in the subject at school certificate level has been persistently low. It is suspected that this low performance could be attributed to a number of factors which includes gender.

Gender differential is believed to have influenced performance in physics in secondary schools over the years. However, researchers are not unanimous on the direction of the influence between female and male learners in Nigeria. Bello, Opaleye and Olatunde (2018) found out that there was no significant difference between male and female students' perception of difficult concepts in the subject. Adeoye (2010) reported that females performed better than males in physics especially when the test items were based on physics concepts that require learners' low numeracy ability. However, the reverse is the case when the test is based on physics concepts that require learners of higher numeracy ability. Uwem and Macmillan (2016) indicated that the level of perceived difficulty of concrete concepts in physics differs by gender in favour of males particularly when they are subjected to test in difficult abstract concepts. Mwangi (2018) found out that boys perform better in chemistry and physics as compared to girls. Fatoki and Taangahar (2021) however found that students' performance in physics is appallingly low and differ in favour of males.

As a result of the inconsistencies in the findings of earlier studies, this study therefore sought to establish secondary school physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult and the perception of their performance in the subject.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in the study:

- i. What is the physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult?
- ii. What is physics students' perception of their performance in difficult physics concepts?
- iii. What is the difference between physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult and the perception of their performance in the subject?
- iv. What is the difference between male and female physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult?
- v. What is the mean difference between male and female physics students' perception of their performance in difficult concepts in physics?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- i. Physics students' mean perception score of difficult concepts in physics does not significantly differ from the mean perception of their performance score in the subject.
- ii. Physics students' perception of difficult concepts in physics does not significantly differ based on gender.
- iii. Physics students' perception of their performance in physics does not significantly differ based on gender

Research Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive-survey design. The rationale for this design is that the study gathered, already existing information about students' perception and performance, for description and interpretation. The sample size for this study comprises 150 participants out of 1917 students in Makurdi Local Government Area. The study adopted multi-stage sampling. The sample was first stratified into school's ownership of public, private and mission in 11 council wards. The second stage was the selection of 5 science secondary schools using simple random sampling of hat and draw from the school ownerships. Names of schools were written on pieces of paper squeezed, shuffled and picked. The procedure yielded the five schools used. At the final stage, one intact science class from each of the five sampled secondary schools was used. The five classes provided the 150 students used for the study.

A researcher-structured questionnaire named Students' Perception of Difficult Concepts and the Perception of their Performance in the Physics Questionnaire is the main instrument for the study. The Students' Perception of Difficult Concepts and the Perception of their Performance in the Physics Questionnaire was divided into three sections A, B and C. Section A sought for data on respondents' demography. Section B consists 10 items on Students' Perception of Difficult Concepts in Physics ranging from item 1 to 10 while section C has items on Students' Perception of their Performance in Physics ranging from item 11 to 20. Respondents were required to indicate the extent to which they perceive the concepts as difficult as well as the perception of their performance using Likert-type format questionnaire. The questionnaire provided respondents with options of VH = Very High (4), H = High (3), L = Low (2) and VL = Very Low (1). Concepts perceived as difficult were scored high while those perceived as not difficult were scored low. A high mean score in students' perception of their performance in physics meant that the concepts were not difficult whereas a low mean score in the perception of their performance meant that the concepts were perceived as difficult.

The instrument was validated by two experts in the Department of Science and Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria. The instrument was trial-tested on twenty respondents of a school with same characteristics as the schools used in the main study. The reliability of the two sections (B and C) of the instrument, determined by Cronbach Alpha statistics, scored a reliability coefficient of 0.62 and 0.75 respectively. These coefficients were high enough for the instruments to be reliably used for the study.

The copies of the instrument were administered by face-to-face distribution and collection. All questionnaires were returned, collated and analyzed. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the hypotheses. The cut-off mean of 2.50 was used for research questions while 0.05 significance level was used for testing of hypotheses.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult?

Table 1: Physics Students' Perception of Physics Concepts as Difficult

	Items on Perception of Physics Concepts as Difficult	\bar{x}	δ	Remarks
1.	My perception of Scalars and Vectors as difficult is ...	2.83	0.89	H
2.	My perception of Position, Distance and Displacement as difficult is ...	2.81	0.87	H
3.	My perception of Work, Energy and Power as difficult is ...	2.81	0.86	H
4.	My perception of Heat Energy as difficult is ...	2.93	0.80	H
5.	My perception of Electric Charges as difficult is ...	2.87	0.81	H
6.	My perception of Gravitational Field as difficult is ...	2.93	0.74	H
7.	My perception of Waves as difficult is...	2.89	0.70	H
8.	My perception of Equilibrium of Forces as difficult is ...	2.92	0.71	H
9.	My perception of Projectile as difficult is ...	2.94	0.79	H
10.	My perception of Gas Laws as difficult is ...	2.81	0.79	H
	Cluster Mean	2.87	0.79	H

Note: H = High; L = Low

The results in Table 1 show that the mean score of physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult was high. This yielded a high cluster mean in physics of 2.87 above a benchmark of 2.50 for taking decision. This indicates that the level to which Physics students perceive physics concepts as difficult was high.

Research Question 2

What is the physics students' perception of their performance in difficult physics concepts?

Table 2: Mean Scores of Physics Students' Perception of their Performance in Difficult Physics Concepts

Items on difficult Concepts	\bar{x}	δ	Decision
11 My perception of performance in Scalars and Vectors is ...	1.71	0.65	L
12 My perception of performance in Position, Distance and Displacement is ...	1.87	0.71	L
13 My perception of performance in Work, Energy and Power is ...	1.75	0.60	L
14 My perception of performance in Heat Energy is ...	1.82	0.62	L
15 My perception of performance in Electric Charges is ...	1.83	0.62	L
16 My perception of performance in Gravitational Field is ...	1.81	0.58	L
17 My perception of performance in Waves is ...	1.86	0.66	L
18 My perception of performance in Equilibrium of Forces is ...	1.81	0.58	L
19 My perception of performance in Projectile is ...	1.95	0.70	L
20 My perception of performance in Gas Laws is ...	1.94	0.72	L
Cluster Mean	1.84	0.64	L

Data on Table 2 show that the mean score of physics students' perception of their performance in physics of 1.84 was low. The cluster mean which was below the 2.50 benchmark, for perception of performance of physics students in the subject, was low.

Research Question 3

What is the difference between physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult and the perception of their performance in the subject?

Table 3: Mean Difference between Physics Students' Perception of Physics Concepts as Difficult and the Perception of their Performance in the Subject

Subject	\bar{x} for perception of physics concepts as difficult	\bar{x} for perception of Performance in physics	\bar{x} Diff
Mean scores	2.87	1.84	1.03

Data on Table 3 show physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult with mean of 2.84 and students' perception of their performance in the subject with mean of 1.84. Therefore, a mean difference of 1.03 between physics students' perception in physics concepts as difficult and the perception of their performance in the subject was in favour of students' perception of concepts as difficult.

Research Question 4

What is the difference between male and female physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult?

Table 4: Mean Difference between Male and Female Physics Students' Perception of Physics Concepts as Difficult

Perception of Physics Concepts as Difficult	Male (\bar{x})	Female (\bar{x})	\bar{x} Diff.
Mean (\bar{x})	2.83	2.85	0.02

Data on Table 4 show the difference between male and female physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult was 2.83 for males and 2.85 for females. The mean difference indicates that males have a lower perception of physics concepts as difficult as compared to females by 0.02 in favour of females.

Research Question 5

What is the mean difference between male and female physics students' perception of their performance in physics?

Table 5: Mean Difference between Male and Female Physics Students' Perception of their Performance in Physics in Concepts

Perception of performance	Male (\bar{x})	Female (\bar{x})	\bar{x} Diff.
Mean (\bar{x})	1.85	1.82	0.03

Data on Table 5 show that the mean scores of physics students' perception of their performance in physics was higher with 1.85 for male and 1.82 for female students. The mean difference indicates that males have higher perception of their performance in physics concepts as compared to the perception of females by 0.03. This was in favour of males.

Hypothesis 1

Physics students' mean perception score of difficult concepts in physics does not significantly differ from the mean perception of their performance score in the subject.

Table 6: t-test Analysis of Physics Students' Perception of Physics Concepts as Difficult and the Perception of their Performance in the Subject

Variable	N	\bar{x}	t	d f	Sig.	Decision
Students' perception of difficult concepts	150	2.87				
			40.736	148	0.12	Not Significant
Students' perception of their Performance	150	1.84				

Data on Table 6 show that the t-test value 40.74 is significant at 0.12. Since the significant value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the hypothesis is therefore not rejected. Therefore, physics students' mean perception score of physics concepts as difficult does not significantly differ from the mean perception of their performance score in the subject.

Hypothesis 2

Physics students' perception of difficult concepts in physics does not significantly differ based on gender.

Table 7: t-test Analysis on the Difference Male and Female in Physics Students' Perception of Physics Concepts as Difficult

Group	N	\bar{x}	t	df	Sig.	Decision
Male	74	2.83	-5.45	148	0.69	Not Significant
Female	76	2.85				

Data on Table 7 show that the t-value of -5.45 which is significant at 0.69. Since the significant value of 0.69 is greater than 0.05 alpha value, the hypotheses is therefore not rejected. Therefore, physics students' perception of difficult concepts in physics does not significantly differ based on gender.

Hypothesis 3

Physics students' perception of their performance in physics does not significantly differ based on gender.

Table 8: t-test Analysis on Male and Female Physics Students' Perception of Performance in Physics

Group	N	\bar{x}	t	df	Sig.	Decision
Male	74	1.85	0.88	148	0.09	Not Significant
Female	76	1.84				

Data on Table 8 show that the t-value of 0.88 is significant at 0.09. Since the significant value of 0.09 is greater than 0.05 alpha value, the hypotheses is therefore not rejected. Therefore, physics students' perception of performance of physics does not significantly differ based on gender.

Discussion of Findings

The study established that students' perception of physics concepts as difficult was a high. This implies that physics students perceive concepts in physics as difficult. The finding is in agreement with that of Bello, Opaleye and Olatunde (2018) who posited that physics concepts were mostly considered difficult. The reason for this result is probably due to the complaint that most concepts perceived as difficult have too many formulae and laws to memorize and too many calculations to do, with little or no practical work.

The study also found that physics student's perception of their performance in difficult physics concepts was low. This finding agrees with Abah, Ada and Taangahar (2016) as well as Fatoki and Taangahar (2021) who pointed out that students' performance in the subject has been appallingly low. This could be due to poor teaching methods leading to poor performance in the subject.

The study established a high mean score in students' perception of physics concepts as difficult as compared to a low students' perception of their performance in the subject. The high mean for physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult

showed that the concepts were difficult. This result agrees with Bello, Opaleye and Olatunde (2018) who posited that physics concepts which were mostly considered difficult. The low mean score in the perception of their performance showed that the concepts were perceived as difficult, hence the low mean perception of physics students' performance in the subject. This result also agrees with Abah, Ada and Taangahar (2016) who found an abysmally low students' performance in physics.

The study also revealed that the difference in physics students' perception of difficult concepts in physics does not significantly differ based on gender. This implies that, although both male and female physics students perceive physics concepts as difficult. The finding is in support of Akongu *et al* (2020) who revealed that there is no significant difference in students' perception of physics based on gender.

The findings of this study which showed that physics students' perception of performance of physics does not significantly differ based on gender, implies that gender differential did not exist between male and female in the perception of their performance in physics. The findings are in support of Fatoki and Taangahar (2021) who found that students' performance in physics differ in favour of males.

Conclusion

From the findings it is concluded that students' perception of difficult concepts in physics does not differ from the perception of their performance in the subject and that students' perception of difficult concepts in physics and the perception of their performance in the subject does not depend on gender.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

- i. Even though physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult was high, teachers should enhance student's perception by simplifying the physics concepts through the use of positive attitude towards students when teaching the subject.
- ii. Low physics students' perception of their performance in difficult concepts in physics could require physics teacher to employ appropriate teaching methods to demystify the concepts and improve the perception of their performance in physics.
- iii. The non-gender differential in physics students' perception of physics concepts as difficult and the perception of their performance in the subject should be encouraged by policy makers to reinvigorate the implementation of the policy of gender equality in the study of science.

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